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Evaluation of Child Labor Persistence in the Iraqw Society of Northern Tanzania

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Abstract

In spite of the government's abundant efforts to bring child labor to an end, still, this issue of child labor persists and becomes intolerable. The current study aims at evaluating the child labor persistence in Karatu district in the Iraqw Society of Northern Tanzania. Specifically, the study intended: (i) to assess the extent to which child labor persists in the study area (ii) To find out the causes of child labor in the aforesaid villages (iii) to suggest measures for eradicating child labor in the study area. A sample of 39 primary and secondary school pupils was used in this study. Sixteen (16) key informant interviews involving individual farmers and two focus group discussions among parents, farmers, community leaders, village leaders and district government leaders were also conducted. With respect to the extent of child labor, the exploration depicts that there are still many children working in the coffee farms. The foremost findings of the investigation were that the socio-economic system of the study area advantaged child labor in coffee farms. Nonetheless, the law on this sphere is in opposition to using children as laborers. The investigation divulges that the chief factor that leads children to this social tragedy is socio-economic penury, and earnings for survival are at the core of these aspects. Moreover, characterized in this analysis were some consequences, such as working for extensive hours with very stumpy remuneration. Likewise, for many years, child labor has been a great enemy against the performance of children in academic domains, and many have dropped out of schools. Conversely, the investigation unveils that in the Iraqw community, children contribute significantly to the family economy.

Key words: Child labour, Iraqw people, Tanzania

1. Introduction

Child labor is a persisting social predicament across the world (Baird, Hicks, Kremer, & Miguel, 2016), Harper, 2015). The International Labor Organization (ILO) reported that about 246 million children between the ages of 5-17 engage in child labor (Crowley and Johnson, 2004). In view of the escalating level of the predicament and the magnitude of the consequences allied with these social minors, the government has put in abundant efforts to tackle the problem in the study area. However, they are chiefly multifaceted to delve into due to their concealed and even criminal nature. Slavery, debt repression, trafficking, sexual exploitation, the use of children in the drug trade and in armed conflict, as well as perilous work are all defined as worst forms of child labor (Chadha, 2016).

Promoting Convention No. 182 concerning the prohibition and immediate action for the elimination of the worst forms of child labor, 1999, is a high priority for the International Labor Organization (ILO), which estimates that there are more than 23 million child workers in Africa. An unknown number of these are to be found within the coffee farms, which are claimed to employ more children like any other agricultural cash-crop in the world (Elshof, 1995). In the five (5) to fourteen (14) age groups alone, there are 127 million working children in Asia, 48 million in Africa, 17.4 million in Latin America and the Caribbean, and 13.4 million in North Africa and the Middle East (ICFTU, 2004).

Law against child labor, even if could be enforced, is not the only (or even the best) way to tackle the issue. Child labor legislation must be combined with targeted social and economic incentives (such as for schooling) together with equitable economic growth. On September 30, 1990, the first World Summit for Children promised to reduce child mortality and malnutrition. It set targets to be reached by the year 2000. Though it established no overt objectives on child labor, the targets integrated indispensable education for all children and the completion of primary education by at least 80 percent of children. Meeting these objectives would reduce child labor. The evidence they review shows that education interventions play a key role in reducing child labor and should play a key role in its eventual abolition. But other interventions are also needed, including legislative action, appropriate labor market policies, fertility interventions, and adoptions of technology and better job opportunities for parents. There must also be advocates for better

conditions for working children and for the empowerment of children and their families. An encouraging consensus is emerging - both in the literature and in the policies of international agencies concerned with child labor - that action, to be effective, must aim first to protect children and improve their living and working conditions. This implies a less stigmatized view of child labor, and the recognition that child labor itself can be used as a targeting device to help children through health, nutrition, schooling, and other interventions. In the long term, the objective of eliminating child labor must be approached through legislative action combined with social and economic incentives that take into account not only the types of child labor and child labor arrangements in a country but that country's institutional and administrative capacity. It has been estimated that there are about 215 million child laborers worldwide and the problem is more prevalent in developing countries (FAO & ILO, 2013). Akin to most of the developing countries, Tanzania has been tackled with the crisis of child labor. Following ILO (2010), one out of three children between the ages of 10 and 14 are engaged in child labor in Tanzania particularly in rural areas. Child labor is practiced in farms, mining, domestic works and prostitutes, often under abusive and exploitative conditions, as well as in the tourism sectors. This practice is not only interfering with schooling of the children but also harmful to personal development. In so doing, many children are involved in occupations or activities that may threaten their health and lives (ILO, 2010). Nonetheless, this matter persists in many developing countries including Tanzania. Thus, the study in the course of its succeeding three specific objectives endeavors: i) To assess the extent to which child labor persists in the study area (ii) To find out the causes of child labor in the aforementioned villages (iii) To suggest measures for eradicating child labor in the study area.

2. Child labor persistence in Sub-Saharan Africa

The child labor involved in perilous work and conditions has become overwhelming in Sub-Saharan Africa (Hilson, 2016; Isabella, 2017). The incidence of child labor and the form that it takes are driven by supply and demand factors countrywide, but also by the sheer need of children to survive. In many countries, children are implicated in a number of child labor practices such as prostitution in the commercial and tourism sex industry, forced begging on the streets, and forced soldiering. They may be used as camel jockeys, sweetshop-industry laborers, and cooks and porters for rebels (Ehrenberg & Smith, 2016). A study on child labor trafficking in the Lake Volta fishery of Ghana is

one of the prominent studies which was conducted in order to find out the major causes of this phenomenon, tasks performed by these victims, the recruitment processes involved in this human trade and the condition under which these children work (Vijayarasa, 2013). It further sought to investigate the measures and interventions put in place to curb this unabated problem. An exploratory study approach was adopted which led to the selection of Ogetse, one of the receiving communities along the Lake Volta in the Krachi West district of the Volta region. The data were collected using different data collection strategies and were analyzed qualitatively. Various theories of poverty were used in this study to explain the findings (Townsend, 2014).

Apparently, the scheme involvement is not ample and multi-sectoral in its approach and the livelihood support for children and for their families is not practical. Furthermore, the beneficiary students were better than the non-beneficiary ones in their school attendance, promotion and repetition rates and their academic performance. Thus, the project attainment seems somewhat successful. Consequently, the study advocates enhancement on the nature and level of interventions into a comprehensive and multi-sectoral approach and the demanding nature of the link between livelihood support and intervention for a long lasting effect. Furthermore, the objective of the project should be practical at all levels to respond efficiently to the requirements of children, their families and to sustainably decrease child labor in the study area (Mitiku, 2008).

Numerous studies on child labor have been conducted in Tanzania. One study examined whether and to what extent child labor affects educational attainment in adulthood. While there is a substantial body of literature investigating child labor, long-run effects remain almost entirely unexplored due to the lack of panel data spanning a sufficiently long period of time. This study used a newly available 13 year individual level panel data set from rural Tanzania to show that child labor reduces educational attainment in adulthood. Individuals who had worked an average amount as children (18 hours a week) attain just over half the number of years of education in adulthood compared to those who had not worked. This loss of education translates into a 7 percent point loss in the long-run consumption growth. The impact of child labor is, however, found to be substantially smaller among those who were already attending school at the time of the baseline survey (Krutikova, 2006; Baird et al., 2016). The major finding emanating from this study is that, child labor is a

reflection of poverty and therefore tackling poverty will have a positive impact on child labor. This suggests that policies such as a ban on child labor in rural areas could have adverse effects as child labor decisions are more likely a response to poverty and survival requirements (Akkaro and Mtweve, 2011).

The evaluation of the nature of working environment and conditions in both districts revealed that there were various hazards and risks facing working children. The hazards and risks were derived from the nature of natural surroundings, working conditions, and tools used. Other hazards and risks emitted from the nature of the materials used, constraints, abuses, emergency and personal care, physical and mental stress. Most of the hazards and risks discussed in this study coupled with other indicators of worst forms of child labor analyzed, thus leading to the conclusion that children working in coffee experience perilous hazards (Ishumi et al., 2001; Sellnow, 2013).

Lack of understanding among plantation/farm owners, village/ward leaders and parents of the definition of child labor was also a problem. This study addressed the extent and magnitude of this problem of child labor in Karatu district. The analysis focused on the activities and tasks performed by working children, the schedule of working and break time, the working environment and conditions, and hazards and risks involved. The study unveiled that, frequently, more boys than girls work in coffee farms and plantations since females in the Iraqw society are traditionally employed in domestic works such as fetching water, cooking food, etc.

3. Materials and methods

The current study was conducted in Karatu district and included primary and secondary school pupils and teachers, their parents, farmers and community leaders. Moreover, it integrated certain workers from Kongoni estate, Mangola Chini, Mangola Juu, Shangirila estate, Tanzania Episcopal Conference (TEC) estate, Jipps farm, Ayaroda farms and Village Officials in Oldiani ward in Karatu district.

This exploration used a cross sectional study design. A sample of 39 primary and secondary school pupils was used in this study. Sixteen (16) key informant interviews involving individual farmers and two focus group discussions were conducted to amass information on child labor devices and the perseverance of child labor in these localities in the Iraqw society. Each focus group consisted of 7

respondents, including parents, farmers, community leaders, village leaders and district government leaders.

The study used mixed methods since it intended to get deeper understanding about the impact of social workers in solving the problem of child labor. Explicitly, the study employed phenomenological approach which paid attention to collecting people's meanings attached to the impact of social workers in alleviating child labor. It is chiefly effectual at bringing to the people's experiences and discernments of the life phenomenon and the meanings this phenomenon has to them (Higgs et al., 2006; Close, 2016)). Moreover, Smith (2017) avers that qualitative research approach is more apposite to employ if the study wants to attain intense understanding of the subject matter. Thus, qualitative approach was accompanied by quantitative approach since certain data were collected in the form of numbers.

All statistical analysis procedures were conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists software. Descriptive statistics, mainly frequency and percentages, were used to describe the characteristics of the study population and explore the child labor persistence.

4. Results and discussion

Table 1 presents the baseline characteristics of the school children included in this study. Out of 39 children, 64.1% were males and 35.9% were females. With respect to age distribution, 8 (20.5%) were between the age of 10 and 12 years; 13 (33.3%) were between the age of 13 and 15 years; and 18 (46.2%) were between the age of 16 and 18 years. This indicates that many children were between 16 and 18 years old. The findings unveil that most of the children [23 (59%)] had primary education; 10 (25.6%) had vocational education; and 6 (15.4%) had dropped from primary school. About 74% of the children were born in the rural area, while 26% were born in town. Furthermore, the findings from interviews and focus group discussion revealed that a large number of children working in coffee farms were born in rural areas and were residing in rural areas; very few were found to be born in urban areas. It was established that, there was some sort of rural-urban migration in coffee growing areas even though it was found to be very minimal. About 54% of the children had stayed in the area for 1-10 years, while 28% of them had stayed for 11-15 years. Along the same vein, 18% of them resided for 16-18 years. This shows that most of the children had migrated from either urban areas or from

other rural areas. Data from focus group discussion indicated that most of the children employed in coffee farms were not residents of the specific villages. The study noted that many boys migrated into the coffee growing villages so as to seek employment in the coffee farms. Another important characteristic addressed in this study was family structure. It was found that, 59% of the children were living with both parents; 28.2% were living with one parent; and 12.8% were living with their guardians.

Table 1: Background Characteristics of the Children (N=39)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	25	64.1
Female	14	35.9
Age		
10-12	8	20.5
13-15	13	33.3
16-18	18	46.2
Education Level		
Primary	23	59.0
Vocational	10	25.6
Primary drop out	6	15.4
Place of birth		
Urban	10	25.6
Rural	29	74.4
Length of stay (Years)		
1-10	21	53.8
11-15	11	28.2
16-18	7	18.0
Family Structure		
Both parents	23	59.0
Single parent	11	28.2
Guardian	5	12.8

Source: Field data, 2017

4.1 The Patterns of Child Labor in the Coffee Farm in Karatu District

The findings of the patterns of the child labor portrayed by children are presented in table 2. Regarding the extent of child labor, 48.7% of the children reported that there were many children working in the coffee farms; 30.8% indicated that there were few children in the coffee farms; and 20.5% said that there were so many children in the coffee farms. Similar responses were obtained from interview and focus group discussion. One respondent during focus group discussion said that, “many children are employed in the coffee farms;

for example, during picking of coffee, one farmer having two acres of coffee may employ up to six children”.

According to John (2015), poverty is a chief reason that triggers off child labor. Our findings indicated that, 54% of the children sought employment in the coffee farms due to poverty; 18% said that they were working in the coffee farms so as to get capital; 13% said that they were working in the coffee farms in order to get money for buying school uniforms and other materials such as pens, exercise books, etc; and 15% revealed that, they were working in the coffee farms due to the failure to proceed with schools.

The nature of child labor was also addressed. Basing on the findings, 72% of them said that, children were working voluntarily; while 28% said that they were forced to work on the coffee farms. Results from focus group discussion and interviews indicated that children were working in the coffee farms voluntarily. One respondent during focus group discussion said that, “we are not forced to work in the coffee farms; we are working willingly; no one is forced, but family problems do force us to work in the coffee farms”.

On the aspect of contract of child workers, 74% of the respondents revealed that children were working in the coffee farms with seasonal contracts, while 26% said that they were working on the daily basis contract. From interviews, the study revealed that children were working in the coffee farms on seasonal oral contract. Most of the children who were paid on daily basis were those who were still studying in primary schools; consequently, they travelled or worked during holidays and weekends so as to get money for buying school uniforms and for assisting their families in buying food. The study noted that child workers who were paid on daily basis got better earnings than those who were paid on seasonal basis because the latter stayed with their employers; as a result, some money was deducted as compensation for food and other costs. These findings are in concomitant with observations made by Ishumi et al. (2001). In their study, it was revealed that children who were being paid daily, weekly and monthly got better earnings than those paid after every six months and yearly.

On the time spent by children working in the coffee farms, the data indicated that 61.6% of the children spent 8 to 12 hours per day; 25.6% spent 6 to 8 hours per day; and 12.8% spent 1 to 5 hours. The analysis established that, children spent almost the whole of their day working

in the coffee farms. During data collection, the exploration observed many child workers waking up early in the morning, around 6 am, and returning home for lunch at around 7.p.m. After lunch, they had to return back to work until 5 or 6 pm. This investigation noted that many children were working long hours because growing coffee involves a lot of tough tasks, while farm owners employ few children who are not proportional to the nature of the work. Coffee growing is a very tough endeavor and it is labor intensive, i.e. it needs more manpower. With respect to payment, 54.6 % of the respondents indicated that children paid between TSH. 200,000/= and TSH. 300,000/=. While 10.3% said that they were paid less than TSH. 100,000/=. Moreover, 33.3% of them indicated that, they were paid more than TSH. 300,000/=. This indicates that, there was variation in payment of the children depending on the capacity of the employers as well as the ability and experience of the child in performing various tasks.

Table 2: The Patterns of Child Labor in the Coffee Farm in Karatu District (n=39)

Extent of Child labor	Frequency	Percent
So many	8	20.5
Many	19	48.7
Few	12	30.8
Reason for Working in the Coffee Farms		
Failure to proceed with school	6	15.4
Poverty	21	53.9
Capital	7	17.9
School uniform	5	12.8
Nature of Child Labor		
Voluntary	28	71.8
Forced	11	28.2
Type of contract		
Seasonal	29	74.4
Daily	10	25.6
Working hours		
1-5	5	12.8
6-8	10	25.6
8-12	24	61.6
Payment		
Less than 100,000	4	10.3
Between 200,000 and 300,000	22	56.4
More than 300,000	13	33.3

Source: Field data, 2017

4.2 Contribution of Child Labor to the Household Economy

Concerning this topic, Table 3 indicates that 67% of the sources of income of the parents/guardians of children working in the coffee farms were growing food crops, while 33% providing casual labor in the farms. This shows that the household economy of the children employed in the coffee farms was poor. None of the parents or guardians grew cash crops like coffee, which is the leading source of fund among the villagers in Karatu district.

The results further showed that 56% of the earnings obtained by children working in the coffee farms were used for supplementing family; 23% of the earnings were saved as capital for starting business; and 21% of the earnings were used for personal effects of the children themselves (For instance, for buying soaps, clothes, and school uniforms). Along the same vein, interview and focus group discussion produced similar findings. One parent during focus group discussion said that:

The children working in the coffee farms contribute much to the household economy. For instance, my son, out of TSH.300,000 which he received in the previous season he brought 200,000 at home for purchasing food and other home consumptions.

Another woman added that:

Since my husband died 3 years ago, I have been depending on the proceeds of my two children who are employed in one of the coffee farms. Sometimes, when there is scarcity of food at home, the employer of my sons gives me food; and then, he deducts some money from my sons' wages for compensation.

Table 3: Contribution of Child Labor to the Household Economy (n=39)

Parents' or Guardian' Source of income	Frequency	Percent
Growing food crops	26	66.7
Providing Casual labor in Farms	13	33.3
Uses of child earnings		
Family income	22	56.4
Capital for business	9	23.1
Personal effects	8	20.5

Source: Field data, 2017

4.3 Effects of and Measures to Eliminate Child Labor in Coffee Farms

When the respondents were asked on the effects of child labor, most of them revealed that child labor had various negative effects on children as 59% of them indicated that child labor made children work in the coffee farms for long hours with low wages. In contrast, 23% of the respondents illustrated that, child labor made children fail to proceed with schools.

Growth stunt was also another effect which was revealed by 10% of the respondents. Such respondents were of the opinion that child labor affected children’s mental and physical growth. On the other hand, 8% of them said that child labor forced most children to stay far away from their families, thus acquiring different behavioral patterns (cf. Table 4).

Regarding the measures to be taken in order to eliminate child labor, 64% of them emphasized that legal action should be taken to farmers and parents in order to eliminate child labor; 21% said that the government should ensure all children are taken to school; and 15% said that education should be provided to farmers on the effects of child labor so as to minimize it. Response from interviews also indicated that, the government should put much emphasis on school attendance and legal action against those who employ children in their coffee farms. The study further discovered that there were some weaknesses in the enforcement of law; for example, the village executive officer failed to rescue children from the coffee farms because of fearing opposition from children’s parents and guardians.

Table 4: Effects of and Measures to Eliminate Child Labor in Coffee Farms

Effects of child labor	Frequency	Percent
Failure to proceed with school	9	23.1
Growth stunt	4	10.3
Staying far from family members	3	7.6
Working long hours with low wages	23	59.0
Measures to Eliminate Child Labor		
Legal action to be taken to both farmers and parents	25	64.1
Provision of education to farmers and parents on effects of child labor	6	15.4
Government should ensure all children are attending school	8	20.5

Source: Field data, 2017

5. Conclusion

The study was conducted in the Iraqw society of Northern Tanzania, particularly in Karatu district since there are many coffee growers. The analysis based on the specific objectives of the study which sought to investigate the nature and extent of child labor in coffee farms in Karatu district, to explore the causes of child labor, to identify the effects of child labor, to explore the contribution of the working children to the household economy, as well as to investigate the interventions/measures taken to alleviate the problem of child labor.

Based on the study findings, it was revealed that poverty was a major cause of child exploitation in Karatu district coffee farms. Other causes include socio-economic hardships that force children to work in the coffee farms in order to pay debts or raise school fees and other money for buying uniforms and other school requirements (Crowley, Johnson, Hamot, Sok, & Brown, 2004). Children execute diverse tasks in these farms such as weeding, harvesting coffee and spraying chemicals to crops. The study confirmed that coffee farms in Karatu district were using children of dissimilar age, ranging from 10-18 years. Moreover, children came from different family backgrounds: majority were living with parents, a few were living with single parents and few were orphans. They all worked like adults. Along the same vein, coffee farms attracted children of diverse educational level such as primary school dropouts, primary school pupils, as well as those with vocational education.

The research concludes that children's rights were being violated in Karatu district coffee farms. The children's basic rights to dignity and freedom from exploitation were being infringed. In due course, child labor negatively affects the physical, mental, educational and moral development of the child. From these parameters, we can have effects such as school absenteeism, school drop-outs, failure to proceed with secondary education, low self-esteem and confidence, poor health and stress, and poor interpersonal communications skills.

Notwithstanding the detrimental effects of child labor to the child himself/herself, the study states that child labor contributes much to the household economy (Lancy, 2015). The study revealed that, the earnings obtained by children assisted their families in purchasing food and saving money for starting businesses such as opening kiosks. These seemingly positive effects of child labor motivated parents/guardians to allow their children to offer labor power in the

coffee farms despite the fact that they (parents/guardians) were fully aware of the negative effects of child labor.

Accordingly, the investigation unveiled that there was the lack of enforcement of laws that protect children from exploitation by the government and other agencies responsible for enforcing all policies and laws concerning child labor. It was also revealed that the educational system was a contributing factor in child labor. Children in farms often do not receive the best education for various reasons. For example, teachers usually do not want to teach in remote parts; hence, in these places, there is very low number of teachers. Similarly, poverty reduction strategies must be put in place and be pursued strongly by both government and civil society in order to empower families so that they can abandon the use of child labor.

Poverty was found to be one of the underlying causes of child labor. Dealing with this root cause of child labor will help in eradicating child labor in its entirety. These poverty reduction schemes can include alternative income generation, income compensatory strategies and educational training for parents. Alternative income generating opportunities can take many forms. Projects may provide skills training for adult family members or assist families in acquiring income producing assets, such as livestock, in order to help these families generate income without relying on children's labor. Moreover, the law enforcers should play their roles considerably; these include civil societies, pressure groups and the government. They must make sure that the children are at school and whoever tries to violate the law should be sent to court or legal action should be taken.

It was further revealed that cultural attitudes are a major determinant of whether children work or attend school. Targeted projects can be used to address social attitudes through awareness-raising campaigns that focus on the extent and nature of child labor, the cost it imposes on children, and the benefits forgone in terms of schooling. By changing attitudes that accept or encourage child labor, such projects aim to encourage families and communities to withdraw children from exploitative work and support investment in children's education. Awareness campaigns on child rights and on the extent of the problem of child labor and abuse should be mounted on a regular basis by all stakeholders. Here, media have a very central role to play.

Thus, the study recommends that labor check up must be made more effective in order to make labor inspection more effective in the fight against child labor. Labor inspectors must be familiar with the problem and be aware of the possible consequences for children. Any significant role in combating child labor inevitably requires labor inspectors to be trained in a number of additional areas, starting with the phenomenon of child labor itself, its prevalence, its range and the desirability of its abolition, as well as the relevant international standards and national regulations. The apposite training of inspectors, therefore, is a critical dimension of effective enforcement. Positive country experiences and best practices, as well as international standards must be used to improve the quality of training so that the inspectorate can respond to its dual role of prevention and protection. Local governments should create other sources of income to rid away from depending solely on the central government. This includes mobilizing community resources (human and non-human) to contribute to the social work practices in their areas. Local governments should acknowledge the efforts of social workers and motivate them to improve both their working and living conditions. Eventually, more research regarding this subject should be undertaken so as to revamp information on this field and sufficient reviews to resolve the degree of child labor in this sphere. The number and nature of damage undergone by child laborers working in the agricultural sector and the data by sex and age should be embarked on. Child labor remains pervasive in the district. Likewise, comparable studies might be conducted in other districts in Arusha region and other regions to explore the comparable predicament for better understanding so as to ease detailed classification in the contribution of social workers in deciphering this social phenomenon.

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